

REINCARNATE

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Dear **changemaker**,

In this new edition, we are pleased to share the progress made as **Reincarnate** enters its final stage. The past months have brought important developments: a productive General Assembly in Warsaw, major scientific outputs, hands-on workshops with our partners, new courses on the Reincarnate Academy, and strong representation at leading conferences in Europe and beyond.

Enjoy your reading!

PROJECT UPDATES

Media Coverage and Recognition

Too Valuable for the Landfill: Our coordinator [TU Berlin](#) published a feature highlighting Reincarnate's circular vision for construction & the project's work to move the sector beyond "build-use-demolish." The article highlights robotic dismantling, AI-supported material optimisation, reuse-ready façade strategies and Ragn-Sells' digital inventory efforts.

[Find out more](#)

At this year's [Forum Bauinformatik \(FBI\)](#), hosted by RWTH Aachen University, our colleague **Begüm Aktas** from our coordinator [Technische Universität Berlin](#) received the **Best Paper Award** in the *Sustainability* category for her work "**Matrix-Based Approach to Optimizing Disassembly Sequence Planning for Aluminum-Framed Windows.**"

[Find out more](#)

Reincarnate General Assembly #7- Advancing Circular Construction in Warsaw

On 9–10 October, the consortium met in Warsaw, hosted by Mostostal Warszawa, to review technical progress and prepare the project's final phase. Partners shared updates on how the ten innovations are progressing in the demonstration sites, together with developments on CP-IM, our [Circular Potential Assessment Information Management](#) platform.

[Find out more](#)

INNOVATIVE INSIGHTS

1 Discussion Forum & 2 Workshops

Discussion Forum

Circular approach: at the beginning was... ABC

Autonomous Building for Citizens
Grenoble

The final Discussion Forum, held on **7 May 2025**, examined how circular principles can be implemented in real projects. Speakers from [Akademiska Hus](#), [Bouygues Construction](#) and [DEMO Consultants](#) shared insights on reuse-first strategies, adaptable design, procurement levers, commercial incentives and the need for shared, interoperable data. The exchanges underlined how mindset change, collaboration and practical tools are essential for turning circular construction into standard practice.

[Learn more](#)

Workshops

#1 Reincarnate Workshop on Interfaces to Existing Databases and Planning Tools' innovation

This hands-on workshop, held on **17 June 2025**, was led by [DEMO Consultants](#) and focused on the Digital Delivery Ticket. Participants explored the full workflow from QR-based data capture to BIM enrichment and CP-IM integration. The session showed how structured onsite information strengthens traceability, improves model quality and supports more informed decisions.

#2: Reincarnate Workshop on Future Exploitation Pathways

The workshop on **30 September 2025**, organised by [DEMO Consultants](#), [Ragn-Sells](#) and [Lagemaat](#), focused on circular value-flow planning for flat glass and the one-to-one reuse of prefabricated concrete. Participants mapped value propositions, pains and gains and business model options, supported by recent CP-IM testing during fieldwork in Sweden.

[Learn more](#)[Learn more](#)

SCIENCE AND RESEARCH

New Publications

BIM-Aided Concrete Quantities Estimation & GWP Optimisation

A publication in *Materialy Budowlane* presents the CEMEX Revit plug-in developed within Reincarnate. The tool automates concrete quantity estimation, integrates GWP values and improves sustainability reporting.

[Learn more](#)

Beyond Corrosion – Real-Time Crack & Gas Detection with Robotics and Digital Twins

Presented at NDT-CE 2025, this research showcases an AI-supported, multi-sensor robotic system for real-time inspection of cracks and gas hazards, improving safety and long-term maintenance planning.

[Learn more](#)

Optimising Disassembly Planning for Aluminium-Framed Windows

Presented at EG-ICE 2025, this paper demonstrates automated collision-based modelling to generate disassembly sequences directly from CAD data.

[Learn more](#)

Streamlining BIM-Based Procurement for Circular Economy

A CIB W78 paper presenting the Parametric Design Tool, which automates matching between BIM elements and reclaimed components and integrates GWP calculations to support circular procurement.

[Learn more](#)

New courses from the Reincarnate Academy: Innovation and Upskilling for All

Online course: Integrated Information Management for Circular Value Flow Planning

A module introducing CP-IM data structures, BIM enrichment methods and workflows supporting circular value-flow planning.

[Check it!](#)

Online course: Architectural Design Methods

A course teaching the use of the Parametric Design Tool to match reclaimed components with BIM models, automate updates and evaluate CO₂ savings.

Check it!

REINCARNATE OUTPUTS

This edition **features new deliverables that advance the project's technical foundation** and support circular decision-making, digital integration and lean construction workflows.

D1.3 – Probabilistic Methods for Lifecycle Assessment and Prediction

An approach using IoT sensors, Markov Chains and Bayesian Networks to model degradation, reuse potential and maintenance intervals, adding predictive capability to CP-IM.

[Read it here](#)

D1.4 – Integrated Information Management for Circular Value Flow Planning

Tools and data structures showing how BIM, digital inventories and IoT inputs can be combined through CP-IM to map and optimise reuse and recycling pathways for materials such as flat glass and concrete.

[Read it here](#)

D2.2 – Circular Decision-Making for Extending Use Life

A concise framework for developing renovation scenarios and guiding intervention choices, illustrated through a hypothetical case and prepared for validation in the demonstrations.

[Read it here](#)

[Check all public deliverables](#)

REINCARNATE AROUND EUROPE

Reincarnate partners took part in several major scientific and industry events in Europe and beyond this season.

At [IABIS 2025](#), [Erasmus University Rotterdam](#) presented research on **communication as a driver of circular transformation**.

During [BAM's JF Circular Economy sessions](#), the team presented recent SLAMD results and showed **how the software supports data-efficient material optimisation** with CEMEX and Ragn-Sells.

At [CBSC2025](#) in Lund, [TU Delft](#) presented new methodologies for **long-term adaptive reuse planning**.

At [IAMCR 2025](#), Reincarnate research contributed to discussions on **sustainability narratives in diverse cultural contexts**.

At [CISBAT 2025](#), [DEMO Consultants](#) presented the IFC Whisperer, demonstrating **the potential of knowledge graphs for analysing BIM data**.

At the [RWM Expo 2025](#), [Ragn-Sells](#) engaged with organisations developing **digital tools for traceability** and circular resource management.

At [NDTCE 2025](#), [BAM](#) presented an **AI-supported, multi-sensor robotic inspection** platform designed to support safer maintenance and longer-lived structures.

[Find out more](#)

Follow us and stay tuned!

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